

Dataset				
B	I	N	G	O
Related outputs are cited or linked	Dataset is complete	Data is in open formats	Has license/use statement	Documentation is adequate
Dataset is easy to cite	Confusing or undefined abbreviation	One table per spreadsheet	File names contain spaces or special characters	Contains sensitive information
Variables are understandable	Authorship is clear		Has a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI)	Has documentation
Relationship between files is clear	Origins and methodology are clear	Special equipment or tools are noted	Data file(s) open	Observations are in rows, variables are in columns
Has recognizable file extensions	Meaningful file names	Files are organized	Excel files lack formulas or macros	Consistent file names

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